

Using the production function to account for the intellectual capital of an enterprise

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Аннотация. В работе проведен анализ существующих моделей, отражающих зависимость между выпуском продукции и затратами ресурсов, в ходе которого было выявлено, что основным фактором производства в современных условиях является интеллектуальный капитал. Предложена модернизированная производственная функция, учитывающая важнейшие компоненты интеллектуального капитала – человеческий и информационный. Уточнена структура интеллектуального капитала, определены подходы к его оценке.

Abstract. The work carries out the analysis of existing models, reflecting the dependence between the production release and the resource spend, in the cause of which it was revealed, that the intellectual capital is the basic production factor in modern conditions. Was offered the modernized production function, taking into account most important components of the intellectual capital – the human and the informational ones. Was detailed the structure of the intellectual capital, approaches to its evaluation have been determined.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции в интеллектуальный капитал, инновации, технологии, компетенции, производственный процесс, факторы производства.

Keywords: investment in intellectual capital, innovation, technology, competence, production process, factors of production.

Introduction

As we know from the economic theory, the maximization of the profit is the basic target of enterprise activities. It is achieved by the increase of the production release [14], what requires different resources. The dependence of the production release from the resource spend is determined as the production function. The fundamental problem of the economic science is the economic growth problem. In macroeconomics it is determined as the increase of production and consumption of goods and services [10]. The welfare of all members of the society, the stability of the political system, the place, occupied by the country in the world depend on the solution of this problem.

Main part

Production function models

The production function shows the possibility for the increase of the production release, provided a certain quantity or composition of resources, as well as allows to determine the optimal volume of the production release with different combination of production factors. In order to study and to analyze the influence of different factors on the release were developed several kinds of production function models, having such general view:

$$Y = F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \quad (1)$$

where Y – production release volume;
 x_i – quantity of different kind of resources, spend for the production.

For a rather long time period the dominating hypothesis of the economic science assumed such two determining production factors as labor and capital are enough for the stable development of the economic system [5]. The Cobb-Douglas production

function model, based on this hypothesis explained adequately enough the dependence between the production release and the resource spend:

$$Y = A \times K^a \times L^b, \quad (2)$$

where A – proportionality coefficient;
 K, L – capital and labor quantity, accordingly;
 a – elasticity coefficient by capital;
 b – elasticity coefficient by labor.

The model reflects the extensive economic growth sufficiently enough, when the release increase requires additional resources, including the capital, forwarded to the production extension and to the workforce. In 1942 Jan Tinbergen modernized the Cobb-Douglas model, having supplemented the production function (2) with the element, taking into account the scientific & technical progress [7]:

$$Y = A \times K^a \times L^b \times e^r \quad (3)$$

where r – elasticity coefficient of the production release, depending on rates of the scientific & technical progress;
 e – base of the natural logarithm.

The production function can also take the time factor into account, in such case the model becomes a dynamic one and looks like:

$$Y(t) = A \times K(t)^a \times L(t)^b \times e^{rt}, \quad (4)$$

where t – constantly measured time.

Jan Tinbergen's production function shows that the economic system can be developed as well without the attraction of the adequate quantity of the capital and labor resources. Fixed assets of the enterprise, withdrawn due to the natural wear, are re-

placed by the new, more productive equipment, while positively influencing the production release and taken into account by the r elasticity coefficient. The model assumes that the scientific & technical progress unconditionally and unavoidably positively influence the final result of enterprise activities. It does not depend on trends of innovative processes.

However, the production release is influenced by factors, which are not increasing nor the capital volume neither the number of employees. To such can be referred: new technologies; new methods of the production organization; the qualification of enterprise employees; new methods of the promotion of goods and services in the market etc. These factors are partially registered in the accounting, where intangible assets represent the intellectual capital of the enterprise.

Intellectual capital and its structure

To the intellectual capital of the enterprise some theoreticians refer the trade mark of the company (brand), consumers' loyalty [11], the accumulated knowledge of employees and other factors, which can be classified on the basis of principles, offered by T. Stewart [6] (see fig.1).

The organizational capital of the enterprise consists of the complex of technologic and production processes, the design and technical documentation, software production management complexes, as well as patents, utility models etc. The human capital refers directly to the enterprise employee. It comprises the qualification, education, professional skills and competences of the employee, his/her abilities for the development and practical implementation of the acquired knowledge.

Fig. 1. Principles of the building of the intellectual capital structure

The consumer capital characterizes relations between the organization and the environment: consumers of production and services, suppliers of necessary resources, local government authorities and competitors.

E. Brooking offered structure of the intellectual capital more sophisticated. It comprises four

assets: human assets, intellectual property, infra-structural assets, market assets [2].

The structure, comprising two components – the internal and the external one, seems more comfortable for the modeling and analysis of processes [3] (see fig.2).

Fig. 2. Binary structure of the intellectual capital of an enterprise

The organizational and the human capital represents the internal environment of an enterprise

and the consumer capital forms it links with the exterior environment. Notwithstanding the simplicity

and the adequacy of this structure some secondary importance, given by it to the human capital quality in the production process, can be considered as its shortage.

Modeling of the intellectual capital of an enterprise

The quality of the influence of the human capital on the economic growth has been evaluated in works of R. Lucas and of H. Uzawa [12]. They have offered the following Lucas-Uzawa model:

$$Y(t) = A \times K(t)^a \times [u \times H(t)]^{(1-a)} \times h(t)^{-b}, \quad (5)$$

where u – share of the population, engaged in the production;

$h(t)^{-b}$ – external effect from the average education level in economics;

a – release elasticity by the physical capital;

$H(t)$ – integrated stock of the human capital, determined from the expression:

$$H(t) = h(t) \times L(t), \quad (6)$$

where $L(t)$ – population, equal to labor resources in economics;

$h(t)$ – qualification level of employees.

The peculiarity of the Lucas-Uzawa model is that it is mainly oriented to the human capital and pays a great attention to the education, as to the basic quality criteria, but it does not consider other factors, which can influence the release of production and services. Nowadays there are several approaches to the quantity and quality evaluation of the human capital, among which following ones can be highlighted:

- at the macrolevel is used the human capital development index, which represents the integral index, taking into account the lifetime, the gross domestic product per head, the level of the education, culture etc.;

- at the microlevel the human capital of the enterprise is evaluated as the totality of qualities of each employee, comprising the qualification, education, the accumulated experience etc., though there is a point of view, that such approach is not always acceptable, as the relevant organization of the labor at the enterprise stimulates synergetic effects [9].

The human capital of the enterprise can be also evaluated in species, if using the net added value method, offered by F. Milosht [13] in 2014, as well as the method of measurement of the individual value of an employee [4].

The performed analysis of different methods of the evaluation of the intellectual capital showed that in order to build the production function it is expedient to use the binary model, where the human capital plays the key role. It was based on the Stewart model, highlighting the human and the in-

formational capital, comprising both organizational and consumer components. The informational capital of an enterprise comprises not only models of business processes [1], but also technologies, licenses, patents, the client base, the data on suppliers and consumers, the nomenclature and characteristics of the released production, the financial, economic and production system etc. The expansion of the application of digital technologies gave rise to principally new business models, based on the use of the common platform for the exchange of products, services and information [9] between enterprises, in this juncture the role of the intellectual capital in the development of high technology enterprises of the national rocket and space industry will stably grow.

The informational capital can be evaluated in species:

$$IC = IS + IP + DB, \quad (7)$$

where IS – is the value of the informational system of an enterprise, the automated management system of the production of different suppliers, like ERP (SAP, 1C, Oracle etc.), the cost of the installed software, the data base management system (DBMS) etc.;

IP – the value of technologic licenses, know-how, efficiency proposals, technical solutions etc., used at the enterprise;

DB – data bases of enterprise suppliers and consumers.

The intellectual capital can be expressed in the form of the total informational and human capital in species:

$$I = IC + HC, \quad (8)$$

where IC – informational capital;

HC – human capital.

The production function, taking into account the influence of the intellectual capital on the release of production and services, looks as follows:

$$Y(t) = A \times K(t)^a \times L(t)^b \times I(t)^f, \quad (9)$$

where I – intellectual capital;

f – elasticity of the release to the intellectual capital.

The model (9) has got its peculiarities, depending on the specialization, quantity of the released production and the kind of economic activities of an enterprise. The mass and large scale production are characterized by the considerable volume of the released production, which saturates the market within the short time period.

With that the technologic process is rather intensive, causing the wear of the special equipment,

in this juncture mass-based enterprises relatively often upgrade fixed assets and production. As a rule, mass and large scale production technologies assume the automation of all processes, in this juncture requirements for the qualification of workers are not high, what makes it possible for company managers to promptly hire and change the personnel, processes of the upgrading of fixed assets and of the workforce are reflected in the model (9).

Job shops and small scale enterprises are characterized by the high qualification of experts, the high precision universal equipment, the considerable share of expenses for the research and development in the production self-cost, in this juncture the role of the intellectual capital here will be much higher than at other enterprises. In the average and short term period the number of work areas, wages and the property complex of an enterprise are subject to minor changes, what gives reason to take the first part of the production function as the conditional-constant value:

$$A \times K(t)^a \times L(t)^b = C = \text{const.} \quad (10)$$

where C – the technologic coefficient, taking into account the fixed assets and labor resources at the enterprise.

The production function and job shops and small scale enterprises can look as:

$$Y(t) = C \times IC(t)^\alpha \times HC(t)^\beta, \quad (11)$$

where α, β – coefficients of the release elasticity to changes in the informational and human capital accordingly.

Conclusion

The production function model, which takes into account the influence of the intellectual capital on the release of production and services, can be used for the substantiation of the decision making while forming the investment strategy of an enterprise. The production function will show the expected result from investments into both informational and human capital. With the aid of built isoquants of the production function can be evaluated the need for investments in the human and informational capital in order to achieve the scheduled production release.

The model shows that investments, which are minor in comparison with fixed assets of the company, directed to the upgrading of the production organization, the development of new technologies, the upgrading of the software, can considerably influence the production release. It should be highlighted that the process of the implementation of new technologies, of the software and of other novelties should be mandatory accompanied by the

personnel retraining, what requires additional resources.

Investments, directed to the upgrading of the qualification of employees, the personnel training, the creation of more comfort and safe work conditions will allow to increase both the labor efficiency and the production quality. Funds, invested in the increase of the efficiency of the wages payment system, will allow to increase wages and, accordingly, the motivation of most able and prospective employees of an enterprise. Investments in the human capital will increase the competitiveness level at the labor market among potential employees of an enterprise, what will provide the opportunity to involve most qualified experts, workers and managers, so enhancing its value.

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